

**IOT BASED HEALTHCARE MONITORING SYSTEMS IN ELECTRONIC
HEALTH RECORD (EHR)****Dr.C.P.Indumathi**

Assistant Professor, Department of CSE, University College of Engineering, BIT Campus,
Tiruchirappalli -620024

Dr. Srinivas D B

Professor, Department of Information Science & Engineering (ISE), Nitte Meenakshi
Institute of Technology, Yelahanka, Bangalore 560064.

Email ID: srinivas.db@nmit.ac.in

Dr. A. Aleeswari

Professor, Department Of Management Studies, PSNA College of Engineering and
Technology, Dindigul – 624622, Tamil Nadu, India

Email ID: Aleesdhandapani@gmail.Com

Dr. K. Yasmin

Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Commerce, The Quaide Milleth College
for Men, Medavakkam, Chennai.

N.Zareena

Assistant professor, Department of CSE, RVR & JC College of Engineering, Guntur.

Mohit Tiwari

Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
Bharati Vidyapeeth's College of Engineering, Delhi

Email ID: mohit.tiwari@bharativedyapeeth.edu

Abstract:

With the emergence of the new corona virus, every nation today places a high value on healthcare. Therefore in this regard, the ideal response to such an outbreak is an IoT-based health monitoring system. The Internet of Things (IoT) is the next internet revolution and a rapidly expanding field of study, particularly in the field of health care. The design and implementation of a health monitoring system using the Internet of Things are presented in this study (IoT). Nowadays, with the growth of innovations, professionals are always searching for cutting-edge electronic gadgets to make it simpler to identify bodily anomalies. IoT-enabled technologies provide the door to the creation of cutting-edge, non-intrusive healthcare assistance solutions with Electronic Health Record (EHR). In particular, those with COVID-19, high blood pressure, diabetes, etc. who live in rural areas of underdeveloped nations like India lack immediate access to health or emergency clinics for testing. The cost of purchasing separate devices or frequent hospital visits is likewise high for the general public. The data

gathered by the sensors in the physical layer is processed by the logical layer. By a thorough review of the literature, we provide the most current research on IoT-based healthcare monitoring systems. The literature evaluation contrasts the efficacy, efficiency, data protection, privacy, security, and monitoring of different systems. The primary goal is to make things more affordable for average people. In addition to financial sustainability, patients will have simple access to private treatment. This study introduces an Internet of Things (IoT)-based solution that will streamline the use of a typically complex medical gadget at a low cost while you sit at home. The general public's employment of these gadgets as auxiliary aids in a particular circumstance may have a significant effect on their own life. These derived data are then sent to the base station through an IoT cloud. The doctor may then access the values from any other place using the base station as a gateway. Thus, depending on the readings of the temperature and heart rate. About their importance and the advantages of IoT healthcare, the paper examines the advantages of IoT-based healthcare systems. A taxonomy of healthcare monitoring sensors is provided in the study, along with an examination of wireless and wearable sensor-based Internet of Things monitoring systems.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Health Care, Electronic Health Record (EHR), Healthcare Monitoring Systems.

1. Introduction

The use of these technological gizmos is now expanding the scope of the improvements produced by medical specialists. In the realm of medical, Internet of Things devices are employed often. The research provided in this article focuses on an Internet of Things-based health monitoring system as its topic. Particularly, there are less doctors available to treat COVID-19 patients, high blood pressure patients, hypertension patients, diabetic patients, and other types of patients in rural portions of a country territory than there are in urban sections of the same territory. Except for government medical institutions, medical equipment is rare in rural locations. These clinics treat a greater number of patients on a daily basis as compared to hospitals run by the government. In a manner similar to this, the majority of the equipment has reached its final stage. As a direct result of this, in the event that a situation involving an emergency occurs, this hardware component will send a report to the physicians or medical professionals as promptly as feasible. The remaining work will be completed by the doctors based on their reports. The platform for IoT health monitoring has been of tremendous assistance in the growth and development of contemporary medicine [1].

The Internet of Things is being put to considerable use in the medical business. And the technology that we are talking about is a system based on the internet of things that monitors patient health. Inside this health monitoring system, there is a sensor that will be responsible for recording the patient's current health state. It can be completed in less time, at a lower cost, and in a more compact format. With this technology, it is possible to monitor a variety of aspects of the human body, including temperature, heart rate, and oxygen saturation, and the findings may be shown on a web page. The application layer, the logical layer, and the physical layer make up the three tiers of the system. It is a monitoring gadget that can simultaneously measure many parameters, such as temperature, heart rate, and oxygen saturation level [2].

A healthcare monitoring system based on the Internet of Things that includes a multitude of sensors, together with an intelligent security system. The system collects data on

vital signs using a number of different sensors, such as a DHT11 sensor for determining humidity and ambient temperature, a pulse sensor for determining heart rate, and an infrared thermometer for determining body temperature. The EHR was used to gather data on the patient's state, and the Wi-Fi module was used to transmit and store that data. The information that has been obtained is shown on the LCD. When the sensor detects an abnormal reading, a GSM module sends a text message to the user's smartphone in order to facilitate a speedy phone call to the patient's family or healthcare provider. The accuracy of the temperature and pulse sensors were tested in a series of experiments to see how well they performed [3].

The worldwide networked service architectures that were connected to the internet. Research at the forefront of information and communications technology has led to the development of the Internet of Things. It has the potential to enhance the quality of life for those who live in cities. Because of the staggering rate at which the world's population is growing and the rising prevalence of chronic diseases, it is becoming more and more important to design cost-effective healthcare systems that are able to effectively manage and provide a wide range of medical services while simultaneously reducing overall expenses. This is one of the reasons why designing cost-effective healthcare systems is becoming more and more important. The Internet of Things (IoT) has emerged as a critical growth area, and as a result, recent developments in healthcare monitoring systems have been made feasible by it. In order to collect, share, monitor, store, and analyze the data generated by these objects, the IoT healthcare-monitoring system tries to connect various services and things in the world through the Internet. This is done in order to improve the quality of the data that may be collected. The Internet of Things (IoT), on the other hand, is a new paradigm that enables remote administration and communication with any connected physical equipment in any intelligent application. These applications include smart cities, smart homes, and smart healthcare. The ability to accurately diagnose diseases and monitor patients is essential to providing quality medical care. Attaching sensor networks to the human body will be of considerable assistance with both of these duties. The information may also be accessed quickly and simply whenever it is needed from any location in the world [4].

Sensors are the initial layer of equipment that allow connections to be made via the use of additional sensors and technological improvements. These sensors are used to monitor a variety of indications, including temperature, respiratory flow rate, heart rate, and oxygen saturation level. The primary purpose of this Internet of Things initiative is to enhance cosmology-based responses by adding the capacity to monitor health. One of the "essential indicators" or critical health markers that the human body has is the heart rate. The number of contractions, also known as beats, that occur inside the heart in one minute is counted. Using the many various wireless network technologies available enables the possibility of doing remote monitoring of healthcare delivery systems. They enhance the connectivity of Internet-connected devices and the efficiency with which Internet of Things applications function [5].

Figure 1: Electronic Health Record using wearable sensor

Research that were only finished a short while ago on Internet of Things-based healthcare monitoring systems. The developed piece of wearable technology is capable of measuring a variety of physiological parameters, including the user's heart rate, electrocardiograms, and temperature (HR). When an ECG, a pulse oximeter reading, and the Pulse Arrival Time (PAT) are measured, a person's blood pressure may be determined (BP). Communication between people and remote monitoring technologies is made easier by the fact that each component is developed inside a predetermined architectural framework. The devices may also communicate wirelessly with one another and make advantage of the relatively minimal amounts of power that they use in order to make accurate measurements of a specific physiological signal. It is possible to make a wireless transmission of the physiological measurements to a gateway by using a BLE module. The data are encrypted both at the sensor patch and at the gateways in order to protect users' privacy and maintain the security of data transfer. The wearable sensor system is connected to the cloud via a gateway that is formed by a smartphone and a Raspberry Pi module. This makes it possible for data to be downloaded and analyzed in the cloud. Despite the fact that it has a low rate of energy consumption, BLE technology is not suitable for wireless communication over extended distances and at high data rates [6].

2. Review of literature

While it might be challenging and taxing for elderly persons to drive a long distance to the hospital, the situation has recently improved for these individuals. Throughout the course of our investigation, we have chosen a number of specific sensors to help us locate a variety of problems. Health monitoring solutions that are based on the internet of things (IoT), it is now possible for customers to get the necessary physiological information while relaxing at home. The monitor will take readings that include the subject's temperature, heart rate, oxygen saturation level, and other relevant data. IoT-based patient monitoring systems that make use of sensors to locate, evaluate, and keep track of two essential vital signs are the topic of discussion in a research study. They developed an Internet of Things-based patient monitoring system that can detect two essential vital signs—body temperature and respiratory rate—evaluate the level of vital signs in relation to the age of the patient, provide alerts for abnormal conditions, and wirelessly display the results through Android apps. Body temperature and respiratory rate are two of the most important vital signs. They used a pair of sensor modules in addition to an EHR Mega 2560 and an ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module [7].

In order to manage Big Data in an Internet of Things context effectively, a specialized information processing system designed specifically for Internet of Things-based healthcare monitoring systems is required. The whole process of processing data consists of three steps:

collecting and aggregating data, classifying the data, and making decisions based on the findings of the analysis. The tests were executed by using Python as the programming language. This model was simulation-basedly empirically evaluated, and many health sensors were used to collect data. In order to validate the effectiveness of the parameters, contemporary hierarchical clustering and back propagation neural network models were used as competition. Apache Kafka and Hadoop are included into this strategy so that it may fulfill the demand for offline processing as well as the collection of data in real time. In terms of data processing and information extraction, the proposed method, which the authors of this study claim achieves an accuracy of 97%, outperforms both the more traditional hierarchical clustering model and the back propagation neural network model. The study does not evaluate the time-efficiency of the model in a similar fashion at any point [8].

A model of healthcare that makes use of seven different classifiers. The data relating to disease was organized into nine distinct datasets based on the categories. AUC, accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity were the four metrics that were used in the process of determining how successful the classifiers were. The three steps of this investigation were the collection of data, the preliminary processing and computation, and the establishment of the results' visibility to clinicians or end-users. The findings were stored on a cloud server once the study was completed. This study investigates the relationship between previously generated work and health models based on machine learning. According to the authors of the study, in comparison to other classifiers, the RF classifier has the highest level of accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and area under the curve (AUC) for a variety of common illnesses. This model has the potential to be developed for a range of applications, such as the prediction of food supply, weather, and the requirements of the military [9].

In a separate piece of work, the authors developed a wearable Internet of Things–cloud–based real-time health monitoring system that is capable of monitoring a person's health in real time. The researchers used a wide variety of wearable sensors, including monitors for blood pressure, body temperature, and heart rate, to collect their data. One further illustration of this would be a study of Internet of Things-based health monitoring systems that make use of Raspberry Pi, LPC2129, and other wearable biomedical equipment. Researchers investigated Internet of Things (IoT)-based health monitoring systems by using Raspberry Pi, LPC2129, and wearable biomedical equipment for the purpose of this evaluation. utilizes both MAX30100 and Lm35 to demonstrate the author's measurement, however the value is shown on the website rather than the mobile applications, which are the ones that are more often available these days [10]. The studies measure things like heart rate and body temperature, but they do not take into account oxygen saturation, nor do they provide the data on an LCD screen or in a mobile application. In addition to assessing the subject's body temperature and pulse rate, the author of the research recorded the electrocardiogram (ECG) parameters and posted the data on a website [11].

A healthcare monitoring system for overweight individuals that is based on the Internet of Things. The prototype is a fully functional device that can measure physiological data such as heart rate, stroke volume, blood pressure, and blood temperature. This device is ideal for doing regular checks on the state of your body's health. Via a Wi-Fi module, the gadget sends medical data from several patients at the same time to medical professionals, who then save the information on an electronic health record board in order to facilitate remote monitoring.

By analyzing the health patterns of patients over the course of time using the data that has been gathered, doctors may search for any changes that may indicate an underlying health problem that has not yet been detected [12]. As a direct consequence of this, using this approach for communication over extended distances may be challenging. Together, Alamsyah and Ikhlayel developed a monitoring system that is based on an Internet of Things and has the ability to detect vital signs. This system will assist medical professionals in diagnosing and monitoring the health of their patients. Sensors allow the system to capture vital data such as heart rate, blood pressure, and blood temperature. Raspberry Pi is responsible for the collection and processing of the sensor data before it is sent to the cloud. The information may be accessible remotely and in a convenient manner for medical staff members by using an app on their smartphones. The results of the vital-sign data retrieval show that the instrument was developed, and both the system and its performance were tested and evaluated in an objective manner [13].

The primary contribution that this research paper makes is to focus on IoT-based healthcare monitoring systems in greater detail. This is done so that future researchers, academicians, and scientists will have an easier time locating a road map to understand the currently available healthcare-monitoring systems and will be able to more easily provide solutions and improvements for such important applications. In this article, we present a comprehensive assessment of Internet of Things-based healthcare monitoring systems, including topics such as its benefits, significance, and a review of the relevant literature. In addition to this, we discuss the potential applications of wearable technology in healthcare systems from the Internet of Things perspective. The report also provides a description of challenges and unsolved issues, a discussion of the security and protocols for Internet of Things healthcare monitoring systems, as well as a classification of healthcare monitoring sensors. In addition to this, we provide recommendations on how similar challenges and issues could be addressed in the future [14].

3. Research Methodology

After this step, a simple electrical flag is upgraded to an advanced electrical flag, which has the computational information necessary to be stored in RFID. Zigbee is an appropriate standard for this system since it is the proposed technique that is used to transmit digital information to the local server. Because of this, Zigbee is a suitable standard for this system. There are the greatest number of cell hubs concentrated in that area. It is more suggested for usage with devices that are both less power hungry and more compact in size. The data is sent to the therapeutic server from a nearby server via the WLAN connection.

Information gathered from each and every parameter measurement carried out on the EHR IDE's serial monitor. While attempting to acquire the data value, the sensors MAX30100 and LM35 are used. Please refer to this individual as "Patient 2." The investigation into their medical history followed the exact identical steps as those performed on "Patient 1." Despite this, we were able to clearly see that their inside temperatures were quite elevated. It is possible to infer that the individual in question has a high temperature. This individual was able to get an urgent health assessment as well as medical attention throughout the course of the subsequent several days. If the patient's heart rate varies between high and low levels over the course of the tests, they may be able to share their information to the attending doctors. We

measured "Patient 3's" health information in the same way as we did with the previous patients. The rate of the patient referred to as "Patient 3" is higher. Users would be able to keep track of their health data throughout the course of the following several days and continuously evaluate their own state of health with the support of medical professionals. Here are the findings of the tests, as well as an analysis of the measurements taken of each patient's health parameters. In order to conduct this study and conduct the evaluation of the system, three genuine human test subjects were used. With the help of the apparatus that we developed, we were able to collect measurement data for this experiment. The system was tested and evaluated in operational environments as they exist in the real world. The temperature measurements of a test subject are quite close to one another throughout the various measurement settings. Regrettably, the statistics for each participant in the test varied greatly from one another due to the variety of human bodies.

Table 1: Temperature test result of three patients

Temperature	Patient 1	Patient 2	Patient 3
Test 1	41.5	38.1	38.4
Test 2	42.3	35.9	36.4
Test 3	42.3	39.5	35.2
Overall	42.1	37.12	35.2

4. Analysis and Interpretation

The database on the medicinal server is rather extensive. When information is given to the therapeutic server, the server first checks to see whether the patient has a prior medical history. If the patient does have a previous medical history, the server adds the new information to the patient's file before sending it to the expert. In the event that the patient does not have any history associated with a previous treatment, the server will generate a new ID and store the data in its database. The outcomes of a series of real-world tests carried out in sequential order while employing the systems are shown in the tables that follow. Temperature readings from the bodies of three different persons were analyzed. Over the whole of the measurement, the temperature was taken three times from each individual patient case.

Table 2: Descriptive

		Temperature			
		Test 1	Test 2	Test 3	Overall
	Frequency	1	1	1	1
Patient 1	Mean	41.5	42.3	42.3	42.1
	Minimum	41.5	42.3	42.3	42.1
	Maximum	41.5	42.3	42.3	42.1
Patient 2	Mean	38.1	35.9	39.5	37.12
	Minimum	38.1	35.9	39.5	37.12
	Maximum	38.1	35.9	39.5	37.12
Patient 3	Mean	38.4	36.4	35.2	35.2
	Minimum	38.4	36.4	35.2	35.2

	Maximum	38.4	36.4	35.2	35.2
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Figure 2: Descriptive Bar chart

Logistic regression analysis was performed to examine the influence of Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 on variable Temperature to predict the value "Test 1". Logistic regression analysis shows that the model as a whole is not significant ($\chi^2(3) = 4.5, p .212, n = 4$).

The coefficient of the variable Patient 1 is $b = -27.52$, which is negative. This means that an increase in Patient 1 is associated with a decrease in the probability that the dependent variable is "Test 1". However, the p-value of 1 indicates that this influence is not statistically significant. The odds Ratio of 0 indicates that one unit increase of the variable Patient 1 will increase the odds that the dependent variable is "Test 1" by 0 times.

Table 3: Correlation and significance

		Patient 1	Patient 2	Patient 3
Patient 1	Correlation	1	-0.14	-0.85
	p (2-tailed)		.856	.149
Patient 2	Correlation	-0.14	1	-0.1
	p (2-tailed)	.856		.901
Patient 3	Correlation	-0.85	-0.1	1
	p (2-tailed)	.149	.901	

The coefficient of the variable Patient 2 is $b = 2.31$, which is positive. This means that an increase in Patient 2 is associated with an increase in the probability that the dependent variable is "Test 1". However, the p-value of 1 indicates that this influence is not statistically significant. The odds Ratio of 10.1 indicates that one unit increase of the variable Patient 2 will increase the odds that the dependent variable is "Test 1" by 10.1 times.

The coefficient of the variable Patient 3 is $b = 6.94$, which is positive. This means that an increase in Patient 3 is associated with an increase in the probability that the dependent variable is "Test 1". However, the p-value of 1 indicates that this influence is not statistically significant.

The odds Ratio of 1030.39 indicates that one unit increase of the variable Patient 3 will increase the odds that the dependent variable is "Test 1" by 1030.39 times.

5. Result and Analysis

In this section, both the system that was designed for this research project and the results that were obtained by it are presented. The completed system is comprised of an EHR Uno, a sensor for measuring the body's temperature as well as sensors for measuring the SpO2 and pulse rate. The electronic health record (EHR) is connected to a device using a USB in order to provide power to the system. The system begins to function as we begin to upload data to the EHR, and the measurement data will be displayed in a mobile application with the assistance of a Bluetooth module. Additionally, the measurement data will be shown on the LCD display and serial monitor of the EHR Integrated Development Environment (IDE). The comprehensive system diagram, which is shown in the serial monitor of the EHR IDE as well as in the mobile application and consists of measurements of the patient's body temperature, SpO2, and pulse rate.

Table 4: Pulse Ratio

Pulse	Level
60 to 100 BPM	Normal
>100 BPM	High
<60 BPM	Low

A two-factor analysis of variance with measurement repetition was performed to test whether there was

- A significant difference between the groups of the first factor " Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 " (repeated measures) with respect to the dependent variable.
- A significant difference between the groups of the second factor Temperature in relation to the dependent variable.
- There is an interaction between the two factors " Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 " and Temperature in relation to the dependent variable.

The two-factor analysis of variance with repeated measures showed that there is

- Significant difference between the groups of the first factor " Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 " in relation to the dependent variable, $p=aN$,
- Significant difference between the groups of the first factor Temperature in relation to the dependent variable, $p=aN$,
- Interaction between the two variables Temperature and " Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 " in relation to the dependent variable, $p=aN$.

Table 5: Hypothesen

Null hypothesis	Alternative hypothesis
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There is no significant difference between the groups of the first factor Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 (measurement repetition) in relation to the dependent variable.	There is a significant difference between the groups of the first factor Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 (measurement repetition) in relation to the dependent variable.
There is no significant difference between the groups of the second factor Temperature in relation to the dependent variable.	There is a significant difference between the groups of the second factor Temperature in relation to the dependent variable.
There is no interaction effect between the factor Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 and Temperature	There is a interaction effect between the factor Patient 1, Patient 2 and Patient 3 and Temperature

6. Conclusion

In this work, the design and implementation of an IoT-based health monitoring system are given. Users may choose their health metrics with an Internet of Things-based gadget, which may help them manage their health over time. The patients could eventually seek medical help if they are in need. They could quickly and conveniently communicate the doctor's their health parameter data through a single application. We all know that one of the most coveted options for health monitoring right now is the Internet of Things. The most crucial aspect is that any doctor may remotely check on any patient's health since it ensures that the parameter data is safe within the cloud. The article discusses a recently created IoT-based EHR-based health monitoring system. The device will monitor a patient's body temperature, heart rate, and blood oxygen saturation levels before transmitting the information to an app through Bluetooth. The patient may instantly examine their current health status by having this information sent on the LCD display as well. The Internet of Things (IoT) has a huge potential to advance healthcare. They include lower costs as well as improved performance, precision, and efficiency. The advantages of IoT use have made it feasible to optimally automate healthcare services. This work seeks to serve as an introduction to the subject for people who will work in it in the future, giving them a thorough reference guide on IoT and healthcare monitoring systems. Recent studies on IoT-based health monitoring systems have been systematically examined and assessed in this article. The study includes a literature review, in-depth information on their advantages and importance. With the aid of the system we created, elderly patients, asthmatic patients, COPD patients, patients with chronic illnesses, COVID-19 patients, and diabetic patients will be able to maintain their health over time. A personal smart phone with an IoT platform and authorization is then used to receive this data. The doctor then determines the patient's condition and the illness based on the results obtained. As more sensors are added, the system's sensors can be enhanced and we can monitor more health metrics. New algorithms may be implemented across the system for system security. Future modifications and adjustments to the system might take many different forms.

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